

Using MICRODEM to Compare Slope Algorithms

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Introduction

The slope algorithm has evolved with the development of geomorphometry. Comparison of algorithms in the 1990's used a wide range in the number of elevations, from 2 to 9 (Guth, 1995, using MICRODEM; Hodgson, 1998; Jones, 1998). After that point, most software converged on using slight variants that produce nearly identical results from a 3x3 window (Evans, 1980; Horn, 1981; Zevenbergen and Thorne, 1987). In the Evans formulation, this produces identical results to least squares solutions using either a first order (planar) or second order polynomial. The Evans method can be viewed as using the queen's eight nearest neighbors. The Zevenbergen and Thorne method uses the four rook's nearest neighbors, while the Horn method combines the other two by using the queen's neighbors but doubles the weight for the rooks's neighbors.

More recently, suggestions have been made to use larger windows, especially 5x5, and third or fourth order polynomials. These come in part from an effort to create a comprehensive system of curvatures (Minar and others, 2020), and to standardize the definitions and computation of 21 different curvature measures. The larger 5x5 window was alleged to create better curvature maps because of the sensitivity of curvature to DEM errors. The computation of three change of curvature land surface parameters, which are currently not widely used, requires both at least a third order polynomial and a 5x5 window. A tool to compute these curvatures (Feciskanin, 2025) offers only two options, the choice of third or fourth order polynomial in a 5x5 window.

While the use of a single algorithm to compute slope and aspect, curvatures, and change of curvatures has undoubted appeal, the results have to be rigorously compared with the traditional methods, and the use of a simpler algorithm to compute slope and aspect deserves consideration. MICRODEM has recently added the least squares polynomial computations, translating from Fortran to Object Pascal the least squares code from Davis (1973), with the ability to compare the multiple choices in the algorithm for slope.

- Polynomial order, from 1st order (planar) to 4th order.
- Window size (3x3, 5x5, 7x7, 9x9)
- Using all points in the window, versus the 8 queen's neighbors on the outer edge of the window, or all points in the outer edge (or perimeter or boundary) (Ilich and others, 2023; Ilich, 2025).

- Requiring all points in the window to have valid elevations, versus allowing missing data. Of most general importance, this allows extrapolation beyond the edges of the DEM.

The results can be checked using the compiled distribution of MICRODEM (Guth, 2025b), either in the GUI or scripting from the Windows command line, or recompiling the source code (Guth, 2025a) using the free community edition of Delphi (Embarcadero, 2025).

After converting both to percent, the slopes from MICRODEM and LSP Calculator (Feciskanin, 2025) have the same numerical values. For slope and aspect, the first and second order polynomials produce the same numerical result, as do the third and fourth order polynomials (verified in both MICRODEM and LSP Calculator for the third and fourth order; LSP Calculator does not do the lower order polynomials). For curvatures the different order polynomials produce different results.

Table 1 shows how the polynomial order affects the requirements for the least squares solution.

Table 1. Polynomial order requirements for slope and aspect

Polynomial order	Terms in equation	Minimum window	Required elevations in window	Permissible edge extrapolation
2	6	3x3	6 / 9	1 row/column
3	10	5x5	10 / 25	3 rows/columns
4	15	5x5	15 / 25	2 rows/columns

This paper explores the effects for two of parameters in the least squares algorithm.

Effect of Window Size on Slope

Figure 1 shows the significant differences in slope with higher order polynomials and larger window sizes compared to the Evans computation. The larger 7x7 window leads to larger differences compared to the 5x5 window, but even the 5x5 window produces significant differences. The differences occur at breaks in slope, either along ridges or the top of cliffs, where the larger window is more likely to include points with significantly different orientation.

Figure 1. 30 m DTM in Utah, created by mean aggregation from a USGS 1 m DTM. Maps show the hillshade, three polynomial slope maps, and the differences of the higher order estimates to the traditional Evans computation.

Field geology uses dip and strike to measure the local tangent plane to a geological structure; geometrically this is equivalent to slope and aspect (aspect would actually be the dip direction). In Figure 2, consider the point at elevation 1878.2 m on the west side of the ridge near the center of the figure. The smaller 3x3 region lies entirely on the west side of the ridge, and a planar approximation would be appropriate (and the second order polynomial provides the same slope as the plane). The larger 5x5 window extends on the east side of the ridge, and would be expected to have a noticeably different slope—the red vector has a much smaller slope magnitude. The actual steeper slopes from the larger window would not be intuitive for most users, but represents a frequent occurrence for the least squares polynomial as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 2. Downhill vectors for a small area in Figure 1 with 10 m contours. The red vectors are for the third order, 5x5 window polynomial, and the green vectors are for the second order, 3x3 polynomial (Evans). The biggest differences are on the sides of the ridge crest, where the larger window has smaller slopes.

Effects from DEM Points Used

The choice of points to use for the least squares solution only arises for 5x5 or larger windows. The queen's neighbors can only be used for the order 2 polynomial. Figure 3 shows the differences for three algorithms, compared to using all the points in the window. Figure 1 showed the slope maps, and the

differences increase as the polynomial order increases, and the number of points used decreases (the queen’s neighbor method has larger differences compared to using all points on the edge of the window).

Figure 3. Difference in using just the queen’s neighbor points or all the perimeter (edge) points, compared to using all points in the window.

Effects of DEM Edge Extrapolation

The differences among slope algorithms in the major GIS programs are almost entirely along the edges of the DEMs where the computation window extends beyond the DEM. The simplest solution taken by some programs is to avoid extrapolating; if slopes are required to the edge of the DEM, the DEM should be extended. Other programs employ special algorithms along the edges.

Table I shows the number of rows or columns that could have slope extrapolations on the DEM edges, depending on the polynomial order. For testing how large the extrapolation errors would be, MICRODEM allows the slope computation to use only the elevations required to reach the minimum number required for the polynomial order. This treats essentially all points as if they were on the north edge of the DEM, and extrapolates over 1 to 3 rows. It should make no difference whether the extrapolation goes to the east, west, north, or south.

The slope map created with the minimum number of points is computed is compared with that computed required a window with no missing data and thus leaving a buffer of missing data around the margins of the DEM. Figure 4 shows the results, with slope computed in percent. The largest differences

are at the changes in slope. The fourth order polynomial should show larger deviations from a plane, but also extrapolates a smaller distance compared to the third order polynomial.

The mean slope for this DEM is 24% (range 0-200%, using the third order polynomial and the 5x5 window), suggesting that extrapolating slopes to the edges of the DEM should be used with extreme caution.

Figure 4. Edge effects of allowing slope computation with the minimum number of elevations to compute the least squares solution. Differences are for slope computed in percent, comparing windows with the minimum required number of points compared to a full window.

Recommended Slope Algorithm

The results above suggest that for users who only want to compute slope and aspect, the Evans algorithm (faster than the equivalent first or second order polynomial in a 3x3 window) avoids results that would be regarded as sub-optimal for higher order polynomials or larger windows. MICRODEM will compute additional combinations of parameters to see the differences for additional area, and users can determine which algorithm to use.

For users who want to also compute curvatures, more work will be required to compare results: (1) using the same second order polynomial in the 3x3 window as done with slope, eliminating the option to compute change of curvature; (2) using the Evans results for slope, and a larger window and higher order

polynomial for curvature to smooth the results; or (3) using only the larger window and higher order polynomial, and accepting the anomalies for slope shown in this paper. Using changes of curvatures, currently not widely used, drives the algorithm toward larger window and higher order polynomial.

The errors resulting from extrapolation suggest that slope should not be computed along the edges of DEMs. If there are only a few missing elevations distributed within the window, the least squares polynomials should be robust, but that is not the case along the edges of the DEM.

The least squares computation should use all points in the window.

This work considered primarily 1 arc second (~30 m) DEMs. Higher resolution DEMs might require more smoothing, and larger window sizes might be appropriate. For the 1 second DEMs the traditional 3x3 window appears to be the best choice, and the Evans formulation provides faster computational results.

Ultimately, because we cannot determine a true value for slope, the choice of slope algorithms remains a subjective decision. By clearly showing the effects of the parameters that go into the slope algorithm, MICRODEM can help make that decision.

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